

Volume 1

Special Issue

February, 2013

ISSN : 2320 –2645

Quarterly Journal

SHANLAX INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS

No.61, V.P. Complex, 1st Floor
TPK Main Road, Vasantha Nagar,
Madurai – 625 003, Tamil Nadu, India
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Web : www.shanlaxpress.com

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IMPACT OF NON COMMUNICABLE DISEASES IN VIRUDHUNAGAR DISTRICT OF SOUTH TAMIL NADU¹

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Abstract

Non Communicable Diseases (NCDs) are the leading cause of global death and disability. The World Health Organization report 2005 estimates that 60 percent of global mortality is due to NCDs and this figure is projected to increase 17 percent by 2015. Developing nations continue to be ill-equipped to handle this burden and this coupled with poor literacy rates and lack of awareness of disease symptoms result in worse disease outcomes. It is understood that CVD contribute to 24 percent of total deaths and is projected that 30-40 percent of death will be due to CVD by 2020. A study (2001) by Chennai Heart Education and Research Society (CHEARS) at tambaram showed that after the age of 20 years of age, 17.6 percent people develop hypertension, 12.4 percent diabetes, 8 percent develop new disease, 10 percent show abnormal glucose tolerance and 10.4 percent develop coronary artery disease. In a rural camp conducted among children at padappai village near Chennai, 2 percent had rheumatic valvular disease and 30 percent had throat infections. The present study was undertaken in Sivakasi and Sattur Government hospital in Virudhunagar district with secondary data. The study is confined to understand Cardio Vascular Diseases (CVD) Pilot Project in Sivakasi and Sattur Government Hospital, covering a period from October 2007 to January 2010. On an average 806 patients are paying visit to every day. The interdependence between health and economic well-being is well established and there is a huge impact of cardiovascular diseases on economic growth and development. TNHSP should spread awareness about heart diseases and inspire people to shift to healthier lifestyles. The health awareness has helped the patients to aware and understands the health care practices.

Keywords: CVD, NCDs and Counselling.

¹ Paper to be presented at the National Conference on “**Challenges in Health Issues and Public Health Care System in India**” to be held on 21-22th February 2013, organized by Department of Econometrics, School of Economics, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai-625021.

Background

Non Communicable Diseases (NCDs) are the leading cause of global death and disability. The World Health Organization report, 2005 estimates that 60 percent of global mortality is due to NCDs and this figure is projected to increase 17 percent by 2015. NCDs including Cardio Vascular Diseases (CVDs), diabetes, obesity, cancer and respiratory diseases account for 59 percent of the 57 million deaths annually and 46 percent of the global burden of disease (WHO 2008). The percentage of years of life lost attributable to NCDs ranges from low levels of 32 percent in Indonesia (2004) and 46 percent in Vietnam (2004), to as high as 76 percent in Japan and 78 percent in Singapore. The CVDs are 103 in Japan, compared to 279 in China, 295 in Vietnam, and 344 in Indonesia. Progressive urbanization and adoption of a "western" lifestyle contributed to the rising burden of CVD in the developing world (Reddy and Yusuf, 1998, WHO, 1999, and Pais and others, 1996). Developing nations continue to be ill-equipped to handle this increasing burden and this coupled with poor literacy rates and lack of awareness of disease symptoms result in worse disease outcomes (NHSP, 1998). Resultantly all these put severe economic stress on the society particularly in developing countries.

Global research indicates that cardiovascular risk is higher among south Asians than among persons from other regions (Yusuf et al., 2004). A recent study from 52 countries of the world, including Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka, found that south Asians were 6 years younger than the rest of risk factors such as diabetes, high blood pressure and high lipids, and had low levels of protective factors (physical activity and dietary habits). CVD refers to conditions and diseases of the heart and blood vessels, including, but not limited to, Coronary Heart Disease (CHD), heart attack, stroke, high blood pressure, Congestive Heart Failure (CHF) and congenital heart disease. CVD has been the leading cause of death every year since the early 1900's, with the exception of 1918 where influenza was the leading cause of death. In countries such as India, the projected death rates from CVD would be much higher than death rate caused by communicable diseases. In Tamil Nadu, the crude mortality death rate due to CVD is the highest in the country, about 360-430 per/100000.

A study (2001) by Chennai Heart Education and Research Society (CHEARS) at Tambaram showed that after the age of 20 years of age, 17.6 percent people develop hypertension, 12.4 percent diabetes, 8 percent develop new disease and 10 percent develop coronary artery disease. Prevention of CVD is the most effective way of combating the CVD epidemic in the resource poor nations. Moreover, temporal pressure is currently an important worldwide stressor, especially in work contexts. This variable has been studied in relation to different communication channels with cohesion and performance (Gracia, Arcos, & Caballer, 2000; Gracia et al., 2002). High job demands (including time urgency) with low control have been associated with hypertension and increases the long-term risk of myocardial infarction (Karasek & Theorell, 1990; Steptoe & Brydon 2009). The level of education is one of the predictors of knowledge of healthy life styles. The present study work out the CVD pilot project in a Government Hospital with two fold objectives as to study the performance of CVD pilot project in

Sivakasi and Sattur government hospital and to understand the impact of Non Communicable Diseases in Virudhunagar district of South Tamil Nadu.

Data Source

The present study was undertaken in Sivakasi and Sattur Government hospitals in Virudhunagar district with secondary data. The study is confined to understand CVD Pilot Project, covering a period from October -2007 to December-2011. There are nine Government hospitals in Virudhunagar District, namely Virudhunagar, Aruppukottai, Tiruchuli, Kariapatti, Rajapalayam, Watrap, Srivilliputtur, Sivakasi and Sattur and for the present study Sivakasi and Sattur Government Hospital alone was selected. On an average 806 patients are getting treated in these hospitals every day.

CVDs Pilot was carried out in two districts of Sivagangai and Virudhunagar to create awareness among the people. Behavioral Change Communication (BCC) interventions were carried out through School based activity (25 schools in each district) Work place based activity (5 Places in each district) and Community based activity (2 Blocks in each district). While the activities in schools, work place and communities focused on communication for behavioural change, clinic based activities were initiated in 80 Primary Health Centres (PHCs) and 18 Government Hospitals in Sivagangai and Virudhunagar districts to screen persons who visit these facilities to enable early detection and treatment of hypertension. The Gandhigram Institute of Rural Health and Family Welfare Trust (GIRH and FWT), Gandhigram appointed Counsellors under the contract basis with the scale of Rs.5000 for Government Hospital (GH) and Rs.3000 for PHC in March 2008. The GIRH and FWT to celebrate world heart day by rely in sivakasi main town with the help of school children, colleague student and conduted exhibition about the CVD after the end of rely. Tamil Nadu Health System Project (TNHSP) appointed two Staff Nurse to every GH on contract basis in October 2008. The TNHSP implemented communication channels for create awareness among the society. It used various communication channels such bus board, sticker, flux banners, information board, TV/Radio and street theater. Between October 2007 and January 2010, CVD pilot intervention in the two districts screened 11,51,041 persons. Of these, 73,202 persons were suffering from hypertension and they were provided appropriate treatment. It is proposed to extend this programme to other districts in the next three years in collaboration with NCD programme.

Analysis and Discussion

The level of education is one of the predictors of knowledge of healthy life styles. Knowledge is an important pre-requisite for implementing both primary as well as secondary preventive strategies for CVD. The level of knowledge of risk factors for CVD varies among different group of population. The traditional extended family household may not be as updated in current knowledge as a nuclear family household because of a more standard attitude to health beliefs. With increasing urbanization and the problems associated with modern-day living in urban settings, the disease profiles are shifting from infectious to lifestyle-related (IDFC, 2010). It is estimated that by 2015, 50 percent of the spending on inpatient beds would be for lifestyle-related diseases (SHSPL, 2007). A communication strategy applicable in one situation

may not be applicable in another situation. Similarly, what a single medium effective in one place may not be effective in another place. Therefore, an attempt was made to see what is the best combination of media preferred by the illiterate people for giving messages to them.

Table-1: Total No of Cases attending General OP, Screening >30 Yrs and Hypertension from Oct 2007 to Jan 2010

Name of Hospitals	No of Cases attending General OP >30 Yrs	No of screening >30 yrs	To Cases of Hypertension
Sivaksi GH	126959 (49)	22174 (51)	2699 (48)
Sattur GH	132117 (51)	21116 (49)	2956 (52)
Total	259076 (100)	43290 (100)	5655 (100)

Source: Sivakasi and Sattur GH Records from Oct 2007 to Jan 2010.

Note: GH – Means Government Hospital and OP means Out Patients.

The above table shows that total hypertension cases were 5655 from Oct-2007 to Jan-2010. The total no of cases attending general above 30 yrs was 259076. It is high in Sattur government hospital to compare with Sivakasi GH. 43290 cases was screening only out of 259076 cases. In Sattur government hospital only screening 49 percent. Because of the reason this hospital located on the way of National Highway. 52 percent of the people have hypertension in sattur region and remaining 48 percent in Sivakasi region. These patients do not get the counselling before this project was implemented. After the appointment of counselor in March 2008, the number of cases screened above 30 years of age is increased in Sivakasi and Sattur government hospital. TNHSP appointed two staff nurse for CVD pilot project led to the increase in the number of screening cases.

Table-2: Total No of Cases Carried Out Lab and ECG Test from Oct 2007 to Jan 2010

Name of Hospital	Total No of cases carried out Lab Test	Total No of cases carried out ECG Test	To Cases of Hypertension
Sivaksi GH	1513 (47)	1790 (49)	2699 (48)
Sattur GH	1705 (53)	1834 (51)	2956 (52)
Total	3218 (100)	3624 (100)	5655 (100)

Source: Sivakasi and Sattur GH Records from Oct 2007 to Jan 2010.

Note: GH – Means Government Hospital.

47 percent of the cases have Lab investigation In Sivakasi government hospital. Because of the reason, this hospital located three Km away from Sivakasi city bus stand. Also the rural patients have more difficulty to get the bus for treatment. It is understand that the work of counselor in sattur government hospital is very well. Because the total no of cases in lab investigation and ECG was 52 percent to compared with Sivakasi government hospital.

Table-3: Total No of Cases Follow up, Counseled and Control the BP Level Less than 140/90 from Oct 2007 to Jan 2010

Name of Hospital	Total No of Hypertension cases	Total No of Follow Up Cases	Total no of people Counseled	To No of Cases with Blood Pressure <140/90
Sivaksi GH	2699 (48)	1313 (56)	18520 (50)	1118 (59)
Sattur GH	2956 (52)	1031 (44)	18402 (50)	778 (41)
Total	5655 (100)	2344 (100)	36922 (100)	1896 (100)

Source: Sivakasi and Sattur GH Records from Oct 2007 to Jan 2010.

Note: GH – Means Government Hospital

The total number of people counseled was 36922 cases. From Oct-2007 to Dec-2007 there were 555 screened cases who didn't get counselling. The total follow up cases was 56 percent in Sivakasi government hospital and 44 percent in Sattur government hospital. Only 50 percent of the patients have counseling from the counselor in Sivakasi government hospital. After the implementation of communication channels such as Radio, T.V, Poster and counseling, the BP control cases were increasing both Sivakasi and Sattur government hospital. After the dismissal of counselor under this pilot project in March 2010, there are no changes in BP control cases. Because of the pharmacists issue tablets only on particular dates. It leads to decrease in the number of the follow up and BP control cases. In addition to this, the communication channels also inspired the people to know the silent killer of Heart.

The concept of cost of providing health services arises from the fact that goods and manpower are absorbed in the health services which could be used to meet out other needs. In case of health and health services, costs are incurred both by the producers of health services, through their use of staff, building, equipments, materials and supplies etc, and by the consumers who use transport to the health centre's, drugs and special foods etc. overall health service costs should include opportunity costs on both sides. The following table illustrates that total cost for counselling from March-08 to December -2011.

Summary and Suggestion

India is experiencing a rising burden of NCDs. This note described the burden of disease as well the underlying proximate risk factors and their trends. NCDs have become the leading cause of death across most of India. This is accompanied by a reversal of socio-economic gradient of disease burden, where the poorer population is most afflicted, resulting in catastrophic health expenditure and distress financing. To overcome social issues, awareness about CVD should be created among individuals and family members through Information, Education, and Communication. Patients should also be educated about personal and environmental hygiene, secondary prophylaxis, lifestyle modification, and the importance of regular follow-up.

Communication activities can be mediated by counselors, social workers, health visitors, village health nurses, and medical officers of health centers individually or in a group through

role play, storytelling, audiovisual aids, posters, handbills, flash cards, folders and flip charts and through information technology, which may be extended through school health services. Counselor and Staff nurses are instructed to motivate the patients for follow up and spend time for health education on Life Style Modification (LSM) and concentrate only on CVD pilot work. Doctors are requested to write anti hypertension tablet to the patients those who are coming with treatment card and BP check up result. They should motivate the patients to co-operate for all investigations and regular BP checks up. Anti hypertensive drugs should be issued daily to the needy patients to avoid the crowd and to eliminate inconveniences in discharging.

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